

Interfacial Pressure (π) Exerted by Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (NaDS) at Oil Water Interface.

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Equations proposed by Ghosh³ and by Davies¹ to account for the relationship between π and A at oil/water interface have been discussed critically with the help of the data obtained by us on the interfacial pressure exerted by NaDS at a number of oil/water interfaces. There is hardly any difference in the values of π calculated from the equation of Davies and the equation of Ghosh. The values of π calculated from both the equations agree well with those found experimentally only over a certain range of concentration of NaDS investigated.

For the oil-water interface, when the film bears a net electrical charge, Davies¹ has proposed the following equation

$$\pi = \pi_k + \pi_r = \frac{kT}{A - A_0} + \pi_r \quad \dots (1)$$

where π_k and π_r represent the pressure due to the kinetic energy and electrostatic repulsion of the adsorbed long chain ions.

According to Davies

$$\pi_r = 6.1\sqrt{C_1} \left[\text{Cosh Sinh}^{-1} \left(\frac{134}{A\sqrt{C_1}} \right) - 1 \right] \quad \dots (2)$$

or as a simple approximation if $A\sqrt{C_1} < 38$,

$$\pi_r = \frac{2kT}{A} - 6.1\sqrt{C_1}$$

So that

$$\pi = \frac{3kT}{A - A_0} - 6.1\sqrt{C_1} - \frac{2kTA_0}{A(A - A_0)} \quad \dots (3)$$

Ghosh² has used the following equation for the lateral pressure exerted by long chain ions at oil/water interface,

$$\pi = 2n_0kT \left[1 + f \frac{(A - A_0)}{2A} \right] \ln \left(\frac{A}{A - A_0} \right) \quad \dots (4)$$

Later on he has suggested³ that the factor 'f' related to the activity coefficient in equation (4) may be dropped and it may be written in the form

$$\pi = 2n_0kT \left[1 + \frac{(A - A_0)}{2A} \right] \ln \left(\frac{A}{A - A_0} \right) - \frac{6.1\sqrt{C_1}}{1 + \sqrt{C_1}} \quad \dots (5)$$

1. J. T. Davies, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1951, A-208, 224.

2. B. N. Ghosh, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 43, 19.

3. B. N. Ghosh and L. Kundu, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 253.

The interfacial pressure (π) exerted by NaDS at petroleum ether/water interface and *n*-decane/water interface has been studied by Davies and Rideal⁴ and Cockbain⁵. Kling and Lange⁶ and Haydon and Phillips⁷ have also done considerable amount of work on the lowering of interfacial tension by NaDS at *n*-heptane/water interface. We have investigated the interfacial pressure exerted by NaDS at benzene/water, toluene/water and xylene/water interfaces at two different ionic strengths 0.1 and 0.01 at 25°. *A*, the area available per long chain ion has been calculated with the help of Gibbs isotherm in $\frac{1}{RT}$ form i.e.,

$$A = 2.303 \times k \times T \times \frac{d \log C}{d\gamma}$$

since in our experiments there has always been present a sufficient excess of added neutral electrolyte^{6,8}.

EXPERIMENTAL

The interfacial tension (γ) has been measured by Du Noüy tensiometer calibrated by pure liquids at a constant room temperature.

Authors like Speakman⁹, Bartell¹⁰, Harkins and Brown¹¹ have employed different methods to measure γ at liquid-liquid interface. Alexander and Teorell¹² have reported that the ring method can be used with considerable accuracy provided a ring of large diameter is used. The ring supplied by Cenco for 70537 tensiometer has been used by us. Its mean circumference is 6.008 cm.

The scale reading on the dial of the instrument is the apparent surface or interfacial tension. Harkins and Jordan¹³ and Freud and Freud¹⁴ have reported that this value may differ from the true value by as much as 30% in extreme cases though for most measurements the difference is probably less than 5%. The apparent value of the tension (γ_{ap}) must be multiplied by a correction factor (*f*) to know the true value of the tension (γ_{tr}) so that $\gamma_{tr} = \gamma_{ap} \times f$.

Zuidema and Waters¹⁵ have considered the reasons for the correction and have published a formula from which this factor can be determined for a known value of $\frac{R}{r}$ (*R* is the radius of the ring and *r* is the radius of the cross-section of the wire of the ring). Curves

4. J. T. Davies and E. K. Rideal, 'Interfacial Phenomena' 2nd Ed., 1963, Academic Press, New York, p. 211.
5. E. G. Cockbain, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, 50, 874.
6. W. Kling and H. Lange, *Proc. 2nd Internat. Congr. Surface Activities*, 1, 295, Butterworths, London (1957).
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9. J. C. Speakman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1449.
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11. W. D. Harkins and F. E. Brown, *ibid.*, 1919, 41, 501.
12. A. E. Alexander and T. Teorell, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1939, 55, 727.
13. W. D. Harkins and H. F. Jordan, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 1751.
14. B. B. Freud and H. Z. Freud, *ibid.*, 1930, 52, 1772.
15. H. H. Zuidema and G. W. Waters, *Ind. and Eng. Chem.*, 1941, 13, 312.

plotted with practical constants for these factors have been supplied with the instrument by Cenco and from these curves f can be determined directly for a given value of $\frac{R}{r}$, γ_{ap} , d and D . $\frac{R}{r}$ and γ_{ap} are of same significance as mentioned previously, d being the density of air or upper liquid in which the film breaks and D is the density of the lower liquid. Density factors are involved since f is dependent on V , volume of the liquid clinging to the lower part of the ring. Harkins and Jordan¹³ have considered these two factors in detail and first converted the ring method into an accurate one. $\frac{R}{r}$ lying in between 50 and 60 the error is kept minimum as revealed from their works. In our measurements $\frac{R}{r}$ is 54.5.

Knowing γ_{ap} and f , γ can be calculated. The true values (γ_{tr}) thus obtained have been compared with the values obtained by Bartell and Miller's method¹⁰. The difference lies within 1%. Since the correction factor (f) includes the factors considered by the authors^{13,14}, there is no need to make again any further correction.

The sample of NaDS* used is a very pure one and its c.m.c. is 0.0079. Benzene, toluene and xylene used are products of E. Merck and redistilled and are found free from surfactant contamination by surface tension measurement. It is not known whether xylene is a mixture of all the three isomers or a single isomer. The fraction boiling at 138.5° has been collected for our investigation. Double distilled water of specific conductance $0.57 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been used throughout the experiment. NaCl, freed from surfactants by heating, has been used to maintain the ionic strengths at 0.1 and 0.01.

NaDS hydrolyses appreciably on keeping in solution and so all the experiments have been done as quickly as possible so that error due to hydrolysis is reduced to minimum. It has been found that hydrolysis is not appreciable within 24 hr and so there is much less possibility of non-equilibrium conditions during the measurements.

The data are recorded in the Tables I, II and III along with the values of π calculated from the equations (1) taking $\pi_r = 6.1\sqrt{C_i} \left[\text{Cosh Sinh}^{-1} \left(\frac{134}{A\sqrt{C_i}} \right) - 1 \right]$ and (5) for the ionic strength 0.1 and from the equations (3) and (5) for the ionic strength 0.01. The observed values of π have been evaluated from the relation $\pi = \gamma_0 - \gamma$ where γ_0 is the interfacial tension of the aqueous solution of NaCl against the oil and γ is the interfacial tension observed for a particular concentration of the long chain ion, keeping the ionic strength constant.

* The sample of NaDS is a kind gift from Prof. K. J. Mysels.

TABLE I

Interface Benzene—water $\gamma_0 = 34.7$ dynes/cm; Temperature = 25°

Concn. of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	γ observed in dynes/cm	I(a)	Ionic strength = 0.1		
		Area per long chain ion in \AA^2 A	$\pi = \gamma_0 - \gamma$ observed in dynes/cm	π calculated from equation of Davies [$A_0 = 30\text{\AA}^2$]	π calculated from equation of Ghosh [$A_0 = 41.5\text{\AA}^2$]
3.60	23.1	105	11.6	11.6	11.6
1.80	25.7	126	9.0	9.1	9.2
0.90	27.6	151	7.1	7.2	7.3
0.72	28.0	167	6.7	6.3	6.4
0.54	28.9	180	5.8	5.8	5.8
0.36	29.5	210	5.2	4.7	4.7
		I(b)	Ionic strength = 0.01 [$A_0 = 25\text{\AA}^2$]		
27.4	20.4	93	14.3	14.4	14.5
18.3	22.1	105	12.6	12.5	12.5
9.13	24.5	126	10.2	10.1	10.1
4.57	26.7	151	8.0	8.2	8.2
3.65	27.4	167	7.3	7.3	7.3
2.74	27.8	180	6.9	6.7	6.7

TABLE II

Interface—Toluene—water $\gamma_0 = 36.0$ dynes/cm; Temperature = 25°

Concn. of NaDS in gm/mole/l $C \times 10^5$	γ observed in dynes/cm	II(a)	Ionic strength = 0.1		
		Area per long chain ion in \AA^2 A	$\pi = \gamma_0 - \gamma$ observed in dynes/cm	π calculated from equation of Davies [$A_0 = 30\text{\AA}^2$]	π calculated from equation of Ghosh [$A_0 = 41.5\text{\AA}^2$]
5.40	21.9	90.2	14.1	14.2	14.1
4.50	22.8	95.0	13.2	13.2	13.2
3.60	23.6	99.7	12.4	12.4	12.4
1.80	26.7	126	9.3	9.1	9.2
0.90	28.0	158	7.5	6.8	6.9
0.72	28.4	180	7.0	5.8	5.8
0.54	29.3	199	6.5	5.1	5.1
		II(b)	Ionic strength = 0.01 [$A_0 = 25\text{\AA}^2$]		
27.4	21.4	90.0	14.6	15.0	15.0
18.3	23.0	99.7	13.0	13.0	13.3
9.13	25.2	121	10.8	10.6	10.6
4.57	27.7	158	8.3	7.7	7.8
3.65	28.1	172	7.9	7.1	7.0
2.74	28.6	182	7.4	6.6	6.6
1.83	29.5	210	6.5	5.6	5.6

TABLE III

Interface—xylene-water $\gamma_0 = 37.1$ dynes/cm; T temperature = 25°

Concn. of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	γ observed in dynes/cm	Area per long chain in ion Å^2 A	$\pi = \gamma_0 - \gamma$ observed in dynes/cm	III(a) Ionic strength = 0.1	
				π calculated from equation of Davies [$A_0 = 30\text{Å}^2$]	π calculated from equation of Ghosh [$A_0 = 41.5\text{Å}^2$]
5.4	22.1	86.0	15.0	15.1	15.1
4.5	23.0	90.2	14.1	14.2	14.1
3.6	24.0	98.6	13.1	12.6	12.6
1.8	26.7	118.0	10.4	10.0	10.0
0.90	28.9	158	8.2	6.9	6.8
0.72	29.3	169	7.8	6.3	6.2

			III(b) Ionic strength = 0.01		
			[$A_0 = 25\text{Å}^2$]		
27.4	22.9	93	14.2	14.4	14.5
18.3	24.5	105	12.6	12.5	12.5
9.13	26.9	121	10.2	10.6	10.6
4.57	28.8	146	8.3	8.5	8A
3.65	29.3	158	7.8	7.7	7.8
2.74	30.1	195	7.1	6.1	6.1
1.83	30.9	256	6.2	4.4	4.5

DISCUSSION

For the adsorbed long chain strong electrolytes, as is the case here, there is always some uncertainty regarding the value of A_0 to be used in the equation (1) or (3)^{16,17,18}. Davies⁴ himself has used for A_0 the value of 25 or 30Å^2 for NaDS to evaluate π from equation (1) or (3). We have used $A_0 = 25\text{Å}^2$ for the ionic strength 0.01 and $A_0 = 30\text{Å}^2$ for the ionic strength 0.1 as these values of A_0 fit the data best.

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18. J. T. Davies, 'Surface Phenomena in Chemistry and Biology', p. 55, Pergamon Press, London and New York (1958).

There is no such uncertainty regarding the value of A_0 in the evaluation of π from the equation of Ghosh. For the calculation of π from equation (5) we have taken $A_0 = 41.5\text{\AA}^2$ which is in agreement with Cockbain's observation on *n*-decane-water interface at 20° . For a compound like NaDS it has been observed that a surface active ion and its counter ion together at adsorption saturation occupy an area of about 42\AA^2 at the interface².

In the Tables I, II and III the values of π calculated from the eqn. of Davies for both the ionic strengths are recorded in column IV and those calculated from equation (5) are in Column V. There is hardly any difference in the values of π calculated from the two equations. For the two ionic strengths used the values of π calculated from both the equations agree well with those found experimentally over a certain range of concentration of NaDS investigated. In the low concentration region there is appreciable difference between the observed and the calculated values of π .

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